

LOCAL FRACTURE TOUGHNESS PREDICTION OF SHORT AND LONG FIBER COMPOSITES USING SIMULATION OF INJECTION MOULDING AND THE MICROSTRUCTURAL EFFICIENCY MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Local fracture toughness (FT) of short (SGF) and long glass fiber (LGF) reinforced PP was calculated using the microstructural efficiency concept and the MOLDFLOW®- simulation software. The calculated FT was compared which the measured one, which was determined using compact tension (CT)samples. The results showed that for SGF PP reasonable consistence between the predicted and measured FT was found. For LGF PP the difference between these FT- values was higher. This was explained by the assumptions made in the rheological behavior of LGF PP. For SGF PP, however, the microstructural efficiency concept together with the results obtained from the simulation of the fiber orientation can be used for FT optimization of an injection moulded workpiece.

INTRODUCTION

Fracture toughness (FT) of short and discontinuous long fiber composites remains a topic of intensive research. The latter is often motivated by the complex interactions between processing conditions - especially in injection moulding-, the related microstructural details and material properties, and the applied forces in the workpiece. A comprehensive review of the interactions between the microstructure and fracture performance of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics is given in [1]. In this review the microstructural efficiency concept suggested by Friedrich [2] and further developed by Karger-Kocsis [3] is discussed and applied upon various short and long fiber reinforced thermoplastics. The concept is based on two simple relationships:

$$K_{Q,C} = M K_{Q,M} = (A + n R) K_{Q,M} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \sum T_{rel,i} f_{p,eff,i} V_{F,i} (l/d)_{equ,i} (l/d)_{n,i} / (l/d)_{m,i} \quad (2)$$

with $f_{p,eff,i} \approx \alpha [1 + \tanh(\beta f_{p,i})]$ (3)

where $K_{Q,C}$ is the FT of the composite, $K_{Q,M}$ the FT of the matrix, M the microstructural efficiency parameter, "n" the energy absorption coefficient, "A" the matrix stress correction factor and R the reinforcing effectiveness factor. The latter can be described by equ. 2, which includes the fiber volume fraction ($V_{rel,i}$), the relative thickness of the i :th layer ($T_{rel,i}$) related to the total sample thickness B , the effective planar orientation factor ($f_{p,eff}$), the equivalent aspect ratio of the reinforcing fibers $(l/d)_{equ}$, the number $(l/d)_n$ and the mass $(l/d)_m$ average aspect ratios, and α and β as weight factors, of the order 0.5 and 1 to 5, respectively. From the equational description of the concept one can conclude that the processing conditions in injection moulding must affect the magnitude of the composites FT, since they affect the orientation state

and the layer structure of the moulded material. A few examples for this are given in [4], showing that e.g. an increase in the mold temperature and injection speed can significantly increase the composites FT.

Recently commercial software packages e.g. from the company Moldflow were introduced, which simulate the fiber orientation of short fiber composites in injection moulding [5,6]. The object of this paper is to use the commercial software from Moldflow for simulating the fiber orientation and to compare the latter with the real local orientation patterns achieved by microscopic analysis of the injection moulded plates. Further the microstructural efficiency model will be used to calculate local fracture toughness values (based on the local orientations),

Figure 1. Fracture toughness optimization by changing e.g. the material composition or injection moulding parameters

which in turn will be compared with locally measured fracture toughness of the plates. If good consistence between the simulated and measured local FT is found, this concept can be used to optimize a workpiece in its design with respect to local FT (Figure 1).

MATERIALS, PROCESSING AND SIMULATION

The materials used were short (SGF) and long glass fiber (LGF) reinforced PP from Borealis N.V., with 40 wt.% GF respectively. The mould was a simple plate with a size of 80 * 80 * 4 mm³ and the inlet was a film gate with 1 mm thickness. In the simulations and experiments three different injection speeds expressed by various volumetric flow rates were used, namely 1 cm³/s ("slow"), 2,5 cm³/s ("normal") and 5 cm³/s ("fast"). The injection moulding of both materials was performed with a constant melt (260 °C) and mould temperature (40°C). The fiber orientation patterns were analyzed at six different positions, which are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Positions where simulations, calculations and measurements of local fiber orientation and fracture toughness were performed

For the simulation, input data were taken over from a Moldflow "MADRAS"- database file that already existed for a similar 40 wt.% SGF/PP- material. This file contained already data such fiber volume fraction, mean aspect ratio and shear viscosities at six different temperatures and shear rates of 40 wt.-% SGF/PP, which all are needed to simulate the material's behavior in injection moulding. For the LGF PP the input data were the same as for SGF PP except that the mean aspect ratio was set to that of LGF PP and interaction coefficient describing the fiber-fiber interactions during the filling phase was set to zero [6,7]. The authors believe that by doing so some error was introduced to the description of the rheological behavior of LGF PP, but this was accepted due to the lack of more accurate data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The planar orientation factor f_p in its definition requires axisymmetric orientation with respect to the z- axis (thickness). As this fact is not totally true in the real case, it was replaced here by a second order three-dimensional tensor description of the orientation. The range of the values of orientation tensor components (0 to 1) had to be adjusted with the range of the values of the planar orientation factor (-1 to 1) in order to be able to use the same mathematical function for "expressing the hindrance effect of fibers due to their local orientation" [2]. This led to a definition of a new "effective orientation tensor component" $a_{eff,i}$ of the following form:

$$a_{\parallel, \perp eff,i} \approx \alpha [1 + \tanh(\beta (2 a_{jk} - 1))] \quad (4)$$

and

$$R = \sum T_{rel,i} a_{\parallel, \perp eff,i} V_{F,i} (l/d)_{equ,i} (l/d)_{n,i} / (l/d)_{m,i} \quad (5)$$

In equation 4, the a_{22} tensor component must be used for a_{jk} in the case of crack direction parallel to the reference direction (here: melt flow direction (MFD)), whereas a_{11} applies for cracks perpendicular to the reference direction.

The orientation tensor components at each position were calculated from the measurement of the fiber orientation distribution (FOD), which in turn was received from image analysis. The image was adopted from a polished micrograph of the x-y plane with the help of a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and a direct video link to the interactive image analyzer used. The components of the orientation tensor were calculated according to [8]; the calculation routine was developed by Schuster [9]. However, as this image analysis system was not automated, the evaluation of one image was very time consuming. Therefore it was only possible to analyze the fiber orientation at three positions in the thickness direction, namely 0,2 , 1.0 (shear layer) and 2.0 mm (core layer) and for only one image at each position. The size of the analyzed micrographs was $1 * 1 \text{ mm}^2$, which contained about 200 fibers. On the other hand the local orientation tensor components were simulated by Moldflow from a triangular element having a volume of 1.6 mm^3 . The simulated and the calculated orientation tensor components (a_{11} , a_{12} and a_{22}) from the measured FOD's of SGF PP, position C, as obtained for "fast" injection speed, are presented in Figure 3. It shows relatively good consistence between the simulated and measured orientation tensor components a_{11} and a_{22} , yet for a_{12} the measured values seem to be somewhat higher. In this comparison one must note that the tensor components vary from point

Figure 3. Simulated and measured tensor components a_{11} , a_{12} and a_{22} for SGF PP at position C, obtained for a "fast" injection speed

to point in the injection moulded material [10]. Therefore only an analysis of a large number of images can give a good picture of the correlation between the simulated and measured fiber orientation. In Figure 4, simulated values of the tensor component a_{11} of SGF and LGF PP at "fast" and "slow" injection speed are compared with the a_{11} - data determined from the different FOD's. Both figures lead to the conclusion that relatively good correlation exists between the simulated and measured orientation tensor components for the SGF PP, but for LGF PP rather

Figure 4. Simulated and measured tensor component a_{11} for SGF and LGF PP at position C, obtained for "fast" and "slow" injection speed

large discrepancies of the two cases are observed. The other microstructural parameters needed for the calculation of the local reinforcing effectiveness factor R and thus the local FT for SGF and LGF PP are tabulated in Table 1. The simulation software divided the thickness of the plate

Microstructural Parameter	SGF PP	LGF PP
$T_{rel,i}$	0.2	0.2
$(l/d)_{equ,i}$	20	120
$(l/d)_{n,i}/(l/d)_{m,i}$	0.75	0.88
$M = A + n * R$	$3.3 + 0.215 * R$	$3.3 + 0.215 * R$

Table 1. The microstructural parameters used to calculate R and the local FT

into 20 layers. In calculation of R it was assumed that a uniform fiber volume fraction and length distribution through the thickness of the plate existed. The measured FT was determined by using CT- samples of the size $35 * 35 * 4 \text{ mm}^3$, 1 mm/min pulling speed and the ESIS recommendations [11]. The calculated and measured FT's are presented in Figure 5 for SGF and LGF PP, for the case of "fast" injection speed. The scatter of the measured and calculated FT-values was smaller than the drawn symbols in the figure (all FT- values were measured and calculated parallel to the MFD, except for position B, representing transverse crack propagation).

All the results indicate that for all positions and various crack directions quite a good match between the measured and calculated FT's in the case of SGF PP exists. The maximum

difference between the measured and calculated FT-values was found to be 20 % in the case of SGF PP. For LGF PP much higher discrepancies in the measured and calculated FT's were determined. This was not very surprising, because of the assumptions made in the case of the

Figure 5. The predicted and measured FT for SGF and LGF PP, as obtained for "fast" injection speed at different positions of the plate

rheology as input data for the simulation. Additional effects during the flow behavior of LGF PP e.g. elastic bending of fiber bundles with a length of up to 8 mm, are known to be more complex than those of SGF PP [12]. This bundling of the long glass fibers, which is observed in many studies (e.g. [13], Figure 6), decreases the efficiency with which the long fibers resist crack growth. In the fracture process this results to fracture or pull out of glass fibers bundles rather

Figure 6. Glass fiber bundling in LGF PP

than individual fibers, which in the calculation of R decreases the effective aspect ratio of the individual fibers to the one of fiber bundles. The effect of an assumption that the bundling of long fibers decreases the average aspect ratio from 120 to 60 is also presented in Figure 5. If the "corrected" and measured values of LGF PP are compared, this time reasonable prediction accuracy was found for most examined positions.

In order to gain a better correlation between the predicted and measured FT's, the rheology of the SGF and LGF PP's will be studied in the future using an injection moulding machine as a rheometer and establishing more accurate viscosity versus shear rate data. But even then it can not be expected that predictions of the local FT are absolutely precise, since there are still some inaccuracies in the orientation simulation (relative to the real case) [14] and local inhomogeneities such as varying fiber volume fractions in the different layers across the thickness that are so far not part of the simulation. Particularly this is true for LGF PP, where a more complex flow behavior of the material and bundling phenomena complicate the simulation [12]. However the work scheme as presented in Figure 1 can be used for the optimization of FT- trends in a discontinuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic workpiece and can provide useful additional information for the design of the cavity.

CONCLUSIONS

The fracture toughness of injection moulded SGF and LGF PP- composites was predicted and measured using a commercial software package of the company Moldflow for the simulation of fiber orientation together with the microstructural efficiency concept. The results showed that reasonable correlation between the measured and calculated fracture toughness data was found for SGF PP. Due to the complex flow behavior of LGF PP accurate FT- predictions remained difficult.

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